

Training on the Matatag Curriculum and Instructional Readiness of Junior High School Social Studies Teachers in the Schools Division of Calbayog City

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the relationship between the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training and the instructional readiness of Junior High School Social Studies teachers in the Schools Division of Calbayog City during School Year 2025-2026. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed among 183 public Junior High School Social Studies teachers who provided valid responses through printed questionnaires and Google Forms. Data were gathered using a validated researcher-made questionnaire anchored on DepEd MATATAG Curriculum policies, the MATATAG Curriculum Guide, and the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. The instrument demonstrated excellent reliability, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.956 to 0.983. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, independent samples t-test, one-way ANOVA, pairwise comparison,

and Pearson product-moment correlation were used in the analysis. Findings showed that the respondents were mostly 31-40 years old, female, graduate-level prepared, had six to ten years of teaching experience, and had attended two MATATAG-related trainings. The extent of MATATAG Curriculum training was rated very high, with quality of training design, materials, and delivery obtaining the highest composite mean. Instructional readiness was likewise rated very high, particularly in planning meaningful lessons and using learner-centered teaching and assessment strategies. Significant differences in training perceptions were found only by number of MATATAG-related trainings attended. Significant positive relationships were observed between several training dimensions and readiness indicators, especially those involving training quality, competency unpacking, lesson planning, learner-centered strategies, digital integration, and resource development. The study concludes that relevant, well-designed, and sustained MATATAG Curriculum training supports stronger instructional readiness in Social Studies instruction.

Keywords: *instructional readiness, MATATAG Curriculum, professional development, Social Studies teachers, teacher training, curriculum implementation*

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum reform succeeds when teachers are prepared to translate policy directions into classroom practice. In the Philippine basic education context, the MATATAG Curriculum represents a major reform intended to decongest learning competencies, strengthen foundational skills, and improve the quality of classroom instruction. Its phased implementation requires teachers to understand revised learning standards, apply learner-centered strategies, prepare aligned assessments, and develop learning resources that respond to learners' needs. For this reason, teacher training becomes a central mechanism in ensuring that the curriculum is not only disseminated as policy but also implemented meaningfully in instruction.

The MATATAG Curriculum emerged from continuing reforms in the K to 12 Basic Education Program. DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019 emphasized the policy guidelines for the K to 12 program, while DepEd Order No. 013, s. 2023 and DepEd Order No. 010, s. 2024 reinforced learning recovery, curriculum implementation, technical assistance, and capacity-building. These policies recognize that teacher readiness depends on training, learning resources, monitoring, and sustained support from schools and divisions. In Social Studies instruction, the reform is especially important because the subject involves civic values, critical thinking, local and national issues, historical understanding, and meaningful classroom discussion.

Despite the nationwide rollout of the MATATAG Curriculum, teachers continue to encounter implementation concerns related to training adequacy, instructional materials, assessment preparation, competency unpacking, contextualization, and follow-through assistance. Studies on curriculum reform consistently emphasize that professional development must be sustained, content-focused, and connected to teachers' actual classroom work (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Gouëdard et al., 2020; OECD, 2025). In the Philippine context, studies on MATATAG implementation have noted the importance of targeted training, school leadership, resource support, and collaborative mechanisms such as Learning Action Cell sessions (Demate et al., 2025; Herrera, 2025; Toledo, 2025; Ubias, 2024; Yunting et al., 2025).

In the Schools Division of Calbayog City, the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum presents local concerns shaped by access to training, mentoring, technical assistance, and learning resources. Junior High School Social Studies teachers must adjust lessons, unpack competencies, prepare assessments, integrate digital tools, and develop contextualized learning resources. Although studies have explored general teacher perceptions and readiness toward MATATAG implementation, limited evidence has examined how the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training relates to the instructional readiness of Junior High School Social Studies teachers within this division.

This study therefore determined the relationship between MATATAG Curriculum training and the instructional readiness of Junior High School Social Studies teachers in the Schools Division of Calbayog City. Specifically, it described teachers' profile, assessed the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training, measured instructional readiness, tested differences in training perceptions when grouped according to profile variables, and examined the relationship between training dimensions and readiness indicators. The results provide evidence for improving training design, technical assistance, mentoring, and subject-specific professional development for Social Studies teachers.

Literature Review

Teacher Training and MATATAG Curriculum Implementation

Teacher training is a foundational element in curriculum reform because it equips teachers with the knowledge, skills, and confidence needed to implement new expectations. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) emphasized that effective professional development must be sustained, content-focused, collaborative, and grounded in active learning. Villegas-Reimers (2003) similarly explained that continuous professional development enhances instructional competence and teacher confidence. Noe (2017) also described training as a systematic process for improving employee learning and performance, which is applicable to teacher capacity-building in curriculum implementation.

In the MATATAG Curriculum context, training must go beyond orientation. DepEd Order No. 010, s. 2024 calls for training before and during curriculum implementation, technical assistance, monitoring, and resource support. Schleicher (2016) and OECD (2025) stressed that sustained professional learning is more effective than fragmented or one-time training. This is supported by Herrera (2025), who noted that successful MATATAG implementation depends on effective training programs, policy support, and adaptive strategies. Demate et al. (2025) likewise reported that limited training duration, insufficient materials, and weak follow-through contribute to uneven teacher preparedness.

The literature further suggests that the quality of training design, materials, and delivery is critical. Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick (2006) explained that training effectiveness should move from reaction and learning

toward behavioral change and results. In MATATAG implementation, this means that teachers should not only understand the curriculum but also apply it in lesson planning, assessment, resource development, and classroom delivery. Motel (2025), Toledo (2025), and Yunting et al. (2025) similarly emphasized that practical, relevant, and supported training helps teachers gain confidence and readiness in curriculum implementation.

Instructional Readiness in Social Studies Instruction

Instructional readiness refers to teachers' preparedness to plan, deliver, assess, and improve instruction according to curriculum standards. In the MATATAG Curriculum, readiness includes subject matter mastery, competency unpacking, lesson planning, learner-centered instruction, digital integration, and development of aligned learning resources. Almonacid-Fierro et al. (2023) emphasized that pedagogical content knowledge allows teachers to connect subject matter with appropriate instructional strategies, while Shulman (1987) argued that effective teaching requires transforming content into forms understandable to learners.

For Social Studies teachers, readiness requires more than content coverage. Social Studies instruction involves historical, civic, political, economic, geographic, and cultural concepts that must be connected to current issues and community realities. Bihag et al. (2025) highlighted the importance of participatory and contextualized instructional practices in basic education Social Studies. Farhang et al. (2023) also explained that lesson planning supports coherent instruction, while Lestari and Yusuf (2025) stressed the need to align assessment practices with intended learning objectives. These ideas are important because MATATAG implementation requires teachers to unpack competencies into clear learning outcomes and meaningful classroom tasks.

Assessment and classroom management also form part of readiness. Black and Wiliam (2018) emphasized that assessment informs teaching and helps improve learning when used meaningfully. Ahmed and du Plessis (2024) showed that classroom management supports learners' academic performance through organization, engagement, and positive learning environments. Ubias (2024) found that teacher readiness for MATATAG implementation requires school-level support, resource availability, and targeted interventions. Thus, instructional readiness should be understood as a combination of teacher competence, curriculum understanding, learner responsiveness, and institutional support.

Training Support, Technical Assistance, and Curriculum Readiness

Training affects readiness most strongly when it is accompanied by technical assistance and follow-through support. Hall and Hord's (2011) Concerns-Based Adoption Model explains that teachers move from awareness to actual use of an innovation when they receive continuous guidance and opportunities to resolve concerns. Brooks and Brooks (1993) also emphasized that learning is constructed through experience and reflection, which implies that teachers need opportunities to process MATATAG training in relation to classroom realities.

The DepEd MATATAG Curriculum policies underscore the importance of resource packages, monitoring, and technical support (Department of Education, 2023, 2024a, 2024b). Gouédard et al. (2020) likewise described curriculum reform as requiring stakeholder engagement, coherent implementation, and sustained support. In this regard, Learning Action Cell sessions, coaching, mentoring, and division-level technical assistance can help teachers translate training content into classroom practice.

Previous studies converge on the point that readiness is shaped by training quality rather than training attendance alone. Motel (2025) observed that teachers may struggle in content delivery when training lacks depth and practical application, while Toledo (2025) found that school leadership and resource management support stronger curriculum alignment. These findings imply that MATATAG training should be relevant, subject-specific, continuous, and responsive to the actual classroom needs of Social Studies teachers.

Theoretical and Conceptual Anchors

The study was anchored on Constructivist Learning Theory, the Concerns-Based Adoption Model, and Kirkpatrick's Four-Level Model of Training Evaluation. Constructivism explains how teachers actively build understanding through training experiences, interaction, and reflection (Brooks & Brooks, 1993). The Concerns-Based Adoption Model explains how teachers adopt innovations gradually as they receive guidance and move

from concern to effective use (Hall & Hord, 2011). Kirkpatrick's model explains how training quality can lead to learning, behavioral application, and instructional outcomes (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006).

The conceptual framework follows an independent variable-dependent variable structure. The independent variable is the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training in terms of adequacy of training programs, quality of training design, materials, and delivery, and availability of technical support and follow-through assistance. The dependent variable is instructional readiness in terms of subject matter mastery, competency unpacking, lesson planning and delivery, learner-centered teaching and assessment, digital integration, and development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources. Teacher profile variables were used to describe respondents and test differences in training perceptions.

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. The descriptive component was used to determine the profile of respondents, the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training, and the level of instructional readiness. The correlational component was used to examine the relationship between the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training and instructional readiness. Comparative analyses were also conducted to determine whether perceptions of training differed when teachers were grouped according to selected profile variables.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Schools Division of Calbayog City during School Year 2025-2026. The locale was appropriate because the division was implementing the MATATAG Curriculum and Junior High School Social Studies teachers were expected to adjust to revised learning competencies, instructional standards, assessment expectations, and learning-resource development demands.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The respondents were public Junior High School Araling Panlipunan or Social Studies teachers in the Schools Division of Calbayog City. Based on the identified population, 197 teachers were considered as the target respondents. Complete enumeration was used because the population was manageable and directly related to the focus of the study. During the actual conduct of the research, 183 teachers provided valid and usable responses, and these responses served as the final data set. Teachers from private schools, elementary level, senior high school level, and other subject areas were excluded.

Research Instrument

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used as the primary data-gathering instrument. It was developed from DepEd Order No. 013, s. 2023, DepEd Order No. 010, s. 2024, the MATATAG Curriculum Guide, and DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Part I gathered the profile variables: age, sex, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and number of MATATAG-related trainings attended. Part II measured the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training in terms of adequacy of training programs, quality of training design, materials, and delivery, and availability of technical support and follow-through assistance. Part III measured instructional readiness across six dimensions of MATATAG-aligned Social Studies instruction.

The instrument was validated by five experts composed of Social Studies teachers, Master Teachers, and master's degree holders in Araling Panlipunan or Social Science. Their comments were used to refine the clarity, relevance, accuracy, and alignment of the questionnaire items. Reliability testing was conducted with 30 Junior High School Social Studies teachers from the Schools Division of Northern Samar who were not part of the actual respondents. Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranged from 0.956 to 0.983, indicating excellent internal consistency across all dimensions (Masuwai et al., 2024).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured approval from the adviser and panel and requested permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Calbayog City. Coordination was made with district supervisors and school heads of participating public secondary schools. The validated questionnaire was administered through printed survey forms and Google Forms. Respondents were informed of the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of responses. The data collection process lasted approximately two to three weeks. Forty-two responses were gathered through Google Forms, while 141 responses were gathered through face-to-face printed questionnaires, resulting in 183 valid responses.

Data Analysis

Frequency counts and percentages were used to present respondent profiles. Weighted mean was used to determine the extent of MATATAG Curriculum training and the level of instructional readiness. The independent samples t-test was used for sex, while one-way ANOVA was used for age, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and number of MATATAG-related trainings attended. Pairwise comparison was used when a significant difference was found. Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship between MATATAG Curriculum training and instructional readiness. The level of significance was set at 0.05 (Fraenkel et al., 2019).

Ethical Consideration

The study observed voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, and responsible handling of data. Respondents were oriented regarding the purpose of the study and were assured that their identities would not be disclosed. Data were stored in password-protected files accessible only to the researcher and were used solely for academic research purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Junior High School Social Studies Teachers

The study involved 183 public Junior High School Social Studies teachers. Most respondents were 31-40 years old (48.09%), female (69.40%), had completed a master's degree (38.80%) or earned M.A. units (38.25%), had six to ten years of teaching experience (36.07%), and had attended two MATATAG-related trainings (51.37%). These results indicate that the respondents generally possessed professional preparation, classroom experience, and exposure to curriculum-related training that may support MATATAG implementation.

Table 1. *Profile of Junior High School Social Studies Teachers*

Profile variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	30 years old and below	44	24.04
Age	31-40 years old	88	48.09
Age	41-50 years old	38	20.77
Age	51 years old and above	13	7.10
Sex	Male	56	30.60
Sex	Female	127	69.40
Highest educational attainment	Bachelor's degree	39	21.31
Highest educational attainment	Master's degree	71	38.80
Highest educational attainment	Doctorate degree	3	1.64
Highest educational attainment	With M.A. units	70	38.25
Years of teaching experience	1-5 years	40	21.86

Years of teaching experience	6-10 years	66	36.07
Years of teaching experience	11-15 years	49	26.78
Years of teaching experience	16 years and above	28	15.30
MATATAG trainings attended	0	10	5.46
MATATAG trainings attended	1	63	34.43
MATATAG trainings attended	2	94	51.37
MATATAG trainings attended	3	11	6.01
MATATAG trainings attended	4	3	1.64
MATATAG trainings attended	5	2	1.09

Extent of MATATAG Curriculum Training

The overall extent of MATATAG Curriculum training was rated very high, with a grand mean of 4.31. Among the three dimensions, quality of training design, materials, and delivery obtained the highest composite mean of 4.41, followed by adequacy of training programs with 4.28 and availability of technical support and follow-through assistance with 4.23. These findings show that teachers generally perceived the training as organized, relevant, and helpful, although follow-through support ranked slightly lower than training design and adequacy.

Table 2. *Summary of the Extent of MATATAG Curriculum Training*

Training dimension	Composite mean	Interpretation	Rank
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	4.41	Very High	1
Adequacy of training programs	4.28	Very High	2
Availability of technical support and follow-through assistance	4.23	Very High	3
Grand mean	4.31	Very High	

This result supports the view that professional development becomes more effective when it is sustained, relevant, and connected to classroom implementation (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Schleicher, 2016). It also affirms DepEd Order No. 010, s. 2024, which emphasizes training, technical assistance, and support mechanisms during MATATAG implementation. The slightly lower rating for follow-through assistance suggests the need for more regular mentoring, coaching, and subject-specific Learning Action Cell sessions.

Instructional Readiness of Social Studies Teachers

The overall level of instructional readiness was very high, with a grand mean of 4.57. The strongest areas were planning and delivery of engaging and meaningful lessons and use of learner-centered teaching and assessment strategies for diverse learners, both with a composite mean of 4.61. These were followed by development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources (4.59), integration of digital tools and technologies (4.58), subject matter mastery and area of specialization (4.56), and unpacking learning competencies for intended learner outcomes (4.49).

Table 3. *Summary of the Level of Instructional Readiness*

Instructional readiness dimension	Composite mean	Interpretation	Rank
Planning and delivery of engaging and meaningful lessons	4.61	Very High	1.5
Use of learner-centered teaching and assessment strategies for diverse learners	4.61	Very High	1.5
Development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources	4.59	Very High	3
Integration of digital tools and technologies in instruction	4.58	Very High	4
Subject matter mastery and area of specialization	4.56	Very High	5
Unpacking learning competencies for intended learner outcomes	4.49	Very High	6
Grand mean	4.57	Very High	

The very high readiness ratings indicate that Social Studies teachers perceived themselves as prepared to implement MATATAG-aligned instruction. The findings are consistent with Almonacid-Fierro et al. (2023), who emphasized the importance of pedagogical content knowledge, and with Farhang et al. (2023), who highlighted lesson planning as a means of aligning objectives, strategies, and assessments. However, competency unpacking obtained the lowest composite mean among the readiness dimensions, suggesting a continuing need for support in translating curriculum standards into classroom objectives, activities, and assessment tasks.

Differences in MATATAG Training Perceptions by Profile Variables

The test of difference showed that sex, age, highest educational attainment, and years of teaching experience did not significantly influence teachers' perceptions of MATATAG Curriculum training. However, the number of MATATAG-related trainings attended produced a significant difference ($F = 2.659$, $p = 0.024$). The significant pairwise comparison was found between teachers with zero training and those with two trainings (mean difference = 0.63, $p = 0.032$). This indicates that training exposure influenced how teachers perceived the adequacy, quality, and support provided in MATATAG Curriculum training.

Table 4. *Difference in the Extent of MATATAG Curriculum Training by Profile Variables*

Profile variable	Test statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	$t = -0.644$	0.521	Fail to reject H0	Not significant
Age	$F = 0.114$	0.952	Fail to reject H0	Not significant
Highest educational attainment	$F = 0.800$	0.496	Fail to reject H0	Not significant
Years of teaching experience	$F = 2.443$	0.066	Fail to reject H0	Not significant
Number of MATATAG trainings attended	$F = 2.659$	0.024	Reject H0	Significant
Pairwise comparison: 0 trainings vs. 2 trainings	Mean difference = 0.63	0.032	Reject H0	Significant

This finding supports the argument that repeated and meaningful professional learning is more influential than demographic characteristics in shaping teachers' training perceptions (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Hall & Hord, 2011; Schleicher, 2016). The result also aligns with MATATAG-related literature emphasizing that teachers exposed to relevant and context-specific training are more prepared to adapt to the demands of curriculum reform (Herrera, 2025; Yunting et al., 2025).

Relationship Between MATATAG Curriculum Training and Instructional Readiness

Pearson correlation analysis showed that MATATAG Curriculum training was significantly related to several dimensions of instructional readiness. The quality of training design, materials, and delivery showed the

strongest and most consistent relationships, with significant positive correlations across subject matter mastery, competency unpacking, lesson planning and delivery, learner-centered strategies, and digital integration. Adequacy of training programs was significantly related to competency unpacking, lesson planning and delivery, and digital integration. Availability of technical support and follow-through assistance was significantly related to competency unpacking, learner-centered strategies, and development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources.

Table 5. *Relationship Between MATATAG Curriculum Training and Instructional Readiness*

Training dimension	Readiness dimension	Pearson r	p-value	Result
Adequacy of training programs	Subject matter mastery and area of specialization	0.142	0.056	Not significant
Adequacy of training programs	Unpacking of learning competencies	0.401	0.000	Significant
Adequacy of training programs	Planning and delivery of engaging and meaningful lessons	0.374	0.000	Significant
Adequacy of training programs	Learner-centered teaching and assessment strategies	0.186	0.089	Not significant
Adequacy of training programs	Integration of digital tools and technologies	0.325	0.000	Significant
Adequacy of training programs	Development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources	0.118	0.111	Not significant
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	Subject matter mastery and area of specialization	0.453	0.000	Significant
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	Unpacking of learning competencies	0.518	0.000	Significant
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	Planning and delivery of engaging and meaningful lessons	0.471	0.000	Significant
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	Learner-centered teaching and assessment strategies	0.242	0.001	Significant
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	Integration of digital tools and technologies	0.206	0.005	Significant
Quality of training design, materials, and delivery	Development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources	0.174	0.072	Not significant
Technical support and follow-through assistance	Subject matter mastery and area of specialization	0.119	0.109	Not significant
Technical support and follow-through assistance	Unpacking of learning competencies	0.338	0.000	Significant
Technical support and follow-through assistance	Planning and delivery of engaging and meaningful lessons	0.167	0.065	Not significant
Technical support and follow-through assistance	Learner-centered teaching and assessment strategies	0.352	0.000	Significant
Technical support and follow-through assistance	Integration of digital tools and technologies	0.148	0.051	Not significant
Technical support and follow-through assistance	Development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources	0.401	0.000	Significant

The results indicate that training quality matters strongly in strengthening instructional readiness. The strongest relationship was between quality of training design, materials, and delivery and unpacking of learning competencies ($r = 0.518$, $p = 0.000$), followed by training quality and lesson planning and delivery ($r = 0.471$, $p = 0.000$), and training quality and subject matter mastery ($r = 0.453$, $p = 0.000$). These findings confirm that teachers become more ready when training is coherent, practical, and connected to instructional work (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006; OECD, 2025). Non-significant relationships in some areas also suggest that instructional readiness may depend on other factors such as prior academic preparation, teaching experience, availability of resources, and school-based support (Motel, 2025; Toledo, 2025).

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Junior High School Social Studies teachers in the Schools Division of Calbayog City had professional profiles that could support MATATAG Curriculum implementation. Most were in the 31-40 age group, female, graduate-level prepared, had six to ten years of teaching experience, and had attended two MATATAG-related trainings. These characteristics indicate that the respondents generally had academic preparation, classroom experience, and training exposure relevant to curriculum reform.

The extent of MATATAG Curriculum training was perceived as very high. The strongest dimension was the quality of training design, materials, and delivery, while technical support and follow-through assistance ranked lowest among the training dimensions. This means that the training was generally perceived as organized, relevant, and clearly delivered, but sustained coaching, mentoring, monitoring, and Learning Action Cell support remain necessary.

The level of instructional readiness was also very high across all six dimensions. Teachers perceived themselves as prepared in content mastery, competency unpacking, lesson planning and delivery, learner-centered teaching and assessment, digital integration, and development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources. However, competency unpacking obtained the lowest composite mean, indicating the need for additional support in translating curriculum standards into clear objectives, learning tasks, and assessments.

Training perceptions did not significantly differ by sex, age, educational attainment, or teaching experience, but they significantly differed by the number of MATATAG-related trainings attended. Moreover, MATATAG Curriculum training was significantly related to several dimensions of instructional readiness, with training quality showing the strongest and most consistent associations. The findings demonstrate that relevant, well-designed, and sustained training contributes to stronger instructional readiness for Social Studies teachers implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.

Recommendation

The Schools Division Office of Calbayog City should continue implementing sustained and subject-specific MATATAG Curriculum training for Junior High School Social Studies teachers, particularly in competency unpacking, lesson alignment, assessment preparation, and development of MATATAG-aligned learning resources. Education Program Supervisors, Public Schools District Supervisors, and school heads should provide focused technical assistance in translating learning competencies into lesson objectives, classroom activities, and assessment tasks.

School heads should institutionalize regular Learning Action Cell sessions focused on MATATAG Curriculum implementation in Social Studies. These sessions may include collaborative planning, lesson demonstration, assessment preparation, peer mentoring, and discussion of classroom-based implementation concerns. The Division Training and Development unit should also prioritize teachers with no MATATAG training or limited training exposure in future orientation, retooling, and mentoring activities.

Training designers and facilitators should include more Junior High School Social Studies-specific examples, localized lesson activities, competency unpacking outputs, assessment tools, and classroom-based tasks to make training more relevant to the subject area. Schools should also support digital integration by providing training on practical digital tools, offline technology options, and strategies for technology-limited classrooms.

Social Studies departments should promote peer collaboration by tapping teachers with stronger training exposure or graduate-level preparation as peer mentors in lesson planning, resource development, classroom strategies, and assessment preparation. Future researchers may examine MATATAG Curriculum implementation in other divisions, include classroom observations and learner performance data, compare subject areas, or use mixed-method designs to capture deeper teacher experiences and implementation challenges.

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